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**Liberalism and Democracy: Friend or
Foes? Exploring the Complex
Relationship between Individual Rights
and Collective Interests**

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Abstract

The relationship between liberalism and democracy has long been a subject of scholarly debate due to their complex and sometimes contradictory nature. While liberalism emphasizes individual rights, limited government, and personal autonomy, democracy promotes popular participation, collective decision-making, and majority rule. This paper examines the philosophical and political tension between these two frameworks, with a particular focus on the balance between individual rights and collective interests. Using liberal-communitarianism as its theoretical lens, the paper employs critical and comparative methods to evaluate the extent to which liberalism and democracy can coexist as mutually reinforcing ideals. The analysis reveals that while both frameworks share foundational values, such as human rights, the rule of law, and public accountability, their practical application often reveals areas of conflict. In particular, societies marked by deep pluralism frequently experience friction between the pursuit of personal liberty and the demands of collective well-being. Nonetheless, the paper contends that liberalism and democracy are not inherently opposed but can function as complementary forces when properly balanced. The relationship between the two, it argues, is context-dependent and requires continuous negotiation to maintain equilibrium.

Keywords: Liberalism, Democracy, Society, Individual Rights, Collective Interests.

Introduction

The relationship between liberalism and democracy continues to be a subject of enduring debate in political theory and practice. Although often treated as complementary frameworks, liberalism and democracy rest on distinct philosophical foundations. Liberalism champions the primacy of individual rights, personal autonomy, limited government, and the protection of civil liberties (Heywood, 2012; Rawls, 1971). Democracy, by contrast, emphasizes popular sovereignty, collective decision-making, and majority rule (Held, 2006). The convergence of these ideologies in modern political systems has led to the emergence of liberal democracy as the dominant model of governance. Yet, this convergence is neither seamless nor without tension.

Historically, the liberal tradition emerged as a response to absolutist rule, with thinkers such as John Locke and Montesquieu advocating for checks on state power and the protection of individual freedoms through constitutional government (Locke, 1980; Montesquieu, 1989). Democracy, rooted in the classical Athenian polis and revitalized in modernity through the works of Jean-Jacques Rousseau, sought to institutionalize the political agency of the people and uphold collective sovereignty (Rousseau, 1997). The liberal-democratic synthesis, particularly as theorized by John Stuart Mill, attempts to reconcile the individualism of liberalism with the participatory ethos of democracy (Mill, 1859).

Nonetheless, several theorists have raised concerns about the coherence of this synthesis. Critics argue that the liberal emphasis on individual autonomy can conflict with democratic majoritarianism, particularly in deeply pluralistic societies where cultural, religious, and ideological divisions are pronounced (Sandel, 1982; Taylor, 1992). Moreover, liberalism's insistence on procedural neutrality may depoliticize important social struggles and undermine democratic engagement, as argued by scholars such as Mouffe (2000) and Walzer (1983). In response to these challenges, this paper defends a synthesis between liberalism and democracy through the theoretical lens of liberal-communitarianism. The paper is divided into four sections. The first provides conceptual clarification of liberalism and democracy. The second examines their areas of convergence and the key points of divergence between liberalism and

democracy. The final section defends the complementarity of the two theories through liberal-communitarianism of Afisi. It argues therefore that when properly balanced, liberalism and democracy can function as mutually reinforcing frameworks for political order.

Literature Review

The Concept of Democracy

Democracy, like philosophy itself, resists a single, universally accepted definition. Scholars across disciplines continue to debate its scope, essence, and ideal form. As Owolabi (1999) observes, quoting Olaitan, while there exists an almost inexhaustible literature on the concept of democracy, there is a conspicuous absence of scholarly consensus regarding its precise delineation. This, he argues, renders it difficult to promote a single authoritative definition. In his words:

“Whereas an almost inexhaustible literature exists on the concept (democracy), there is a glaring absence of consensus by scholars on the appropriate delineation of the nature and contours of the term such that it is rather difficult to argue for a specific conceptualization of the term as the proper meaning, since democracy is now generally seen as a term with many meanings” (Owolabi, 1999: 4).

Etymologically, the word democracy is derived from the Greek words *demos* (people) and *kratos* (rule), literally meaning “rule by the people” (Pickles, 1970). This classical notion underscores the centrality of popular sovereignty in democratic governance. One of the most widely quoted definitions comes from Abraham Lincoln, who described democracy as “government of the people, by the people, and for the people” (Lincoln, 1863). This formulation emphasizes participation, representation, and the pursuit of the public good.

In contemporary political thought, democracy is commonly understood as a political system in which power is vested in the people, exercised either directly or through freely elected representatives (Merriam-Webster, 2023). This reflects the modern representative model of governance rather than the direct democracy of classical Athens.

Bayo (2000) offers a refined understanding by noting that democracy denotes “popular powers” or rule by the people, in contrast to rule by elites such as the aristocracy or oligarchy. In African political discourse, democracy often takes on unique cultural and socio-political dimensions.

The late Afrobeat musician Fela Anikulapo Kuti famously referred to democracy as the “demonstration of craze,” a critical commentary on how democratic ideals is often perverted in post-colonial African societies.

Similarly, Minogue (1996) reflects on the populist nature of democracy, describing it as a form of rule exercised by the poorer masses against elite or aristocratic interests. This reflects the struggle between the demos and dominant power structures, especially in postcolonial and highly stratified societies.

However, many states today claim the label “democracy” without embracing its ethical and institutional values. As observed by Chilles (2016), the mere existence of regular elections does not suffice to qualify a regime as democratic. He argues: “Regular free and fair elections do not provide for individual freedoms, political equality, female empowerment, an independent civil society, a free press or scope for deliberation—all key components of liberal democracy” (Chilles, 2016:1).

This shows the gap between democratic form and democratic substance, particularly in hybrid regimes where democratic procedures coexist with authoritarian tendencies. Thus, to qualify as a genuine democracy, a political system must reflect both participatory practices and institutional safeguards that ensure accountability, rule of law, protection of rights, and inclusive dialogue.

The Concept of Liberalism

Like democracy, liberalism is a concept that resists narrow or monolithic definition. It is a broad philosophical and political tradition rooted in the defense of individual liberty, constitutional government, and the limitation of state power. Historically, liberalism emerged as a critique of absolutism and feudal hierarchies in early modern Europe, drawing upon Enlightenment values such as rationality, individual autonomy, and human dignity (Gray, 1995). It has since evolved into various strands, classical, social, economic, and neoliberal liberalism, each emphasizing different aspects of liberty and state-market relations.

Etymologically, the term liberalism derives from the Latin word *liber*, meaning “free.” At its core, liberalism holds that individuals possess inalienable rights which must be protected from arbitrary interference by the state or society (Heywood, 2012). John Locke, one of the principal architects of liberal thought, asserted that individuals are born with natural

rights, namely life, liberty, and property, and that governments exist primarily to safeguard these rights (Locke, 1980).

In modern political theory, liberalism is most closely associated with the belief in constitutionalism, rule of law, freedom of expression, and the protection of civil liberties. According to Rawls (1971), a liberal society is one in which the basic structure of institutions guarantees equal basic rights and liberties for all, particularly the most disadvantaged. This formulation introduces a moral dimension to liberalism, focusing not only on individual freedom but also on justice and fairness. In the face of different responses to it, liberalism remains foundational to many contemporary political systems, particularly in its emphasis on the protection of human rights, political pluralism, and institutional checks and balances. In its most developed form, liberal democracy represents an attempt to reconcile the values of liberty and equality, private conscience and public deliberation, individual rights and collective will. In African contexts, liberalism has often been introduced through colonial and postcolonial legal systems. However, its adoption has been met with both adaptation and resistance. African scholars such as Wiredu (1996) and Gyekye (1997) have critiqued liberalism for its Eurocentric assumptions about individuality and have proposed forms of political theory more aligned with African communitarian traditions. Nevertheless, the discourse of rights, personal freedom, and constitutionalism continues to shape political reform across the continent. Nevertheless, the section shall focus on the relationship and the differences between the two theories- liberalism and democracy.

The Relationship and Differences Between Liberalism and Democracy: Toward a Complementary Synthesis

The concepts of liberalism and democracy have often been treated as synonymous in contemporary political discourse. Yet, while they frequently coexist in the modern state, forming what is commonly termed liberal democracy, they emerge from distinct historical origins and are grounded in different normative assumptions. Liberalism is primarily concerned with the protection of individual rights and freedoms, while democracy focuses on popular sovereignty and collective decision-making. The convergence of the two traditions in liberal democracy is not without tensions, prompting political theorists to debate their compatibility, divergence, and practical interdependence. offers a comparative analysis of liberalism and democracy,

discussing their core principles, philosophical foundations, institutional manifestations, and areas of conflict and complementarity. The discussion is grounded in the works of key political theorists such as John Locke, Alexis de Tocqueville, John Stuart Mill, Joseph Schumpeter, Norberto Bobbio, Robert Dahl, Fareed Zakaria, and Chantal Mouffe, whose arguments help illustrate the intellectual contours of this debate.

The Areas of Convergence

One of the differences between liberalism and democracy can be found in the philosophical foundations and historical context of the two. Liberalism emerged in 17th and 18th-century Europe as a reaction against absolutist rule and ecclesiastical authority. Its primary concern is the protection of the individual from arbitrary power, whether from the state, church, or society. As John Locke famously stated in *Two Treatises of Government* (1689:57): “The end of law is not to abolish or restrain, but to preserve and enlarge freedom”. Liberalism advocates for natural rights, limited government, private property, and the rule of law, with freedom of speech, religion, and association being central.

Democracy, by contrast, is rooted in the ancient Greek tradition of popular rule. It was revitalized in the modern era through demands for political inclusion, universal suffrage, and representative institutions. Joseph Schumpeter (1942: 269), redefining democracy in a modern context, described it as: “That institutional arrangement for arriving at political decisions in which individuals acquire the power to decide by means of a competitive struggle for the people’s vote”. Thus, democracy is primarily concerned with political equality and the will of the majority rather than the autonomy of the individual.

The second difference can be found in their conceptual understanding of individual rights and popular sovereignty. In classical liberal thought, the individual precedes society both morally and politically. The liberal tradition, emerging during the Enlightenment, was deeply influenced by the works of John Locke, who wrote that individuals possess natural rights to “life, liberty, and property” that exist prior to the formation of government. Locke (1689:95) asserted: “Men being... by nature, all free, equal, and independent, no one can be... subjected to the political power of another, without his own consent.”

This idea establishes consent and rights, not majority will, as the foundation of legitimate authority. For liberalism, political institutions exist to protect the rights of individuals, not to express a unified collective will. Hence, constitutionalism, rule of law, and individual civil liberties are the hallmarks of liberal institutions. They act as guardrails to prevent both arbitrary state power and majoritarian excesses.

Moreover, the third one is based on the consent and participation. Liberalism prioritizes government by consent, not necessarily through frequent or mass participation, but through legal and institutional guarantees that ensure the individual's autonomy and protection from coercion. This tradition has deep roots in social contract theory, where thinkers like John Locke argued that individuals consent to government to secure their natural rights. Locke famously declared: "Men being, as has been said, by nature all free, equal, and independent, no one can be put out of this estate, and subjected to the political power of another, without his own consent" (Locke, 1689:95).

In this liberal logic, consent is abstract and structural, embedded in constitutions, rights regimes, and the rule of law, rather than constantly renewed through direct political activity. Participation is not the central good; rather, it is one possible means, but not a necessary one, to protect liberty and maintain government accountability.

Thus, in a liberal polity, so long as individual rights, freedom of speech, property, religious liberty, are protected through legal mechanisms, the absence of widespread participation or direct citizen engagement does not inherently delegitimize the state. Minimal government, operating within constitutional boundaries, is often sufficient in liberal thought. Democracy, by contrast, derives legitimacy from the active involvement of citizens in decision-making. Whether through direct democracy or representative systems the exercise of collective will is what gives authority to institutions. Here, political power is justified not by contractual consent, but by the equal participation of all citizens in shaping laws and policies. Robert Dahl, one of the foremost scholars of democratic theory, emphasized this in his definition of democracy as more than just a system of procedures. He wrote: "A key characteristic of democracy is the continuing responsiveness of the government to the preferences of its citizens, considered as political equals" (Polyarchy, 1971: 1).

This emphasis on political equality and responsiveness makes participation not just a mechanism but a principle. Democracy assumes that legitimacy depends on the ability of every citizen to influence government decisions, directly or through representation. As such, voter enfranchisement, competitive elections, freedom of association, and open debate are essential features, not optional enhancements. Furthermore, A core point of contrast between liberalism and democracy lies in their respective approaches to power limitation and decision-making authority. Liberal political theory assumes that unchecked power, whether held by a monarch, legislature, or the people, can become despotic. To prevent this, liberal thinkers have long emphasized the rule of law, meaning that no individual or group is above the law, and that laws must be applied fairly, predictably, and transparently. Montesquieu, a major influence on liberal constitutionalism, famously articulated the idea of separation of powers in *The Spirit of the Laws* (1748), arguing that: “When the legislative and executive powers are united in the same person... there can be no liberty” (Montesquieu, 1989). This insistence on diffusing authority reflects liberalism’s skepticism of concentrated political power, even when that power originates in popular will. For liberals, institutional checks—such as independent courts, bicameral legislatures, and executive restraint. are necessary to prevent both state overreach and majoritarian excesses. By contrast, democracy in its purer form is grounded in the idea that the majority has the right to rule, because the will of the people is the highest political authority. In a purely majoritarian system, the greatest number decides, and this decision carries legitimacy, regardless of its effect on minorities or dissenting individuals. While this approach fulfills the principle of political equality, it also raises the risk of majoritarianism, the idea that the majority can legitimately override the preferences, rights, or protections of the minority. In practice, pure democracy can conflict with liberal protections, especially when laws are passed that restrict freedom of expression, religion, or association, all in the name of popular sovereignty. This tension was famously analyzed by Alexis de Tocqueville in his classic work, *Democracy in America*. While Tocqueville admired the participatory spirit of American democracy, he feared that the majority could become tyrannical when left unchecked. He observed: “If ever the free institutions of America are destroyed, that event may be attributed to the omnipotence of the majority... which breaks the will of the minority and forces it to bend” (Tocqueville, 1835).

Tocqueville's insight was prophetic: democracy without liberal safeguards can devolve into conformity, oppression, and even populist authoritarianism. His analysis reflects the liberal concern that majority opinion, when institutionalized through democratic mechanisms, can become coercive—especially when it suppresses minority voices or restricts civil liberties.

Points of Convergence

Despite these differences, liberalism and democracy often interact positively in political practice. Their convergence has produced what is termed liberal democracy, a system where individual rights and democratic participation are jointly institutionalized. Norberto Bobbio succinctly captures this hybridization: “Liberalism and democracy are like two branches of the same tree, each depending on the other for sustenance” (Bobbio, 1990:34).

In liberal democracies, democratic processes are bounded by liberal constraints: constitutions, bills of rights, judicial review, and independent media. Amartya Sen supports this convergence from a developmental perspective: “Political freedoms and democratic rights are not only essential components of development, they are also instrumental in securing economic security” (Sen, 1999:36).

Thus, liberal institutions can enhance democracy's responsiveness, while democratic participation legitimizes liberal structures.

Also, liberalism and democracy can pull in opposite directions. In times of crisis, security-oriented liberalism may justify limiting democratic input, while populist democracies may attack liberal institutions in the name of majority will. Fareed Zakaria describes the rise of illiberal democracies—regimes that hold elections but violate rights: “Democracy is flourishing; liberty is not. Illiberal democracies gain legitimacy from elections but use that power to rob people of their basic freedoms” (Zakaria, 2003: 17). Yascha Mounk adds that in many contemporary societies: “We are witnessing the rise of democracy without liberalism, and liberalism without democracy—neither of which is sustainable” (Mounk, 2018:41). Such examples show that democracy alone does not guarantee liberty, and liberalism without democratic accountability may become elitist.

Despite their philosophical distinctions, liberalism and democracy share several fundamental principles. First, both value political legitimacy grounded in consent. Second, both promote mechanisms that check

arbitrary power—whether through constitutionalism or electoral accountability. Third, both endorse civil liberties as essential to human dignity and political participation.

Jürgen Habermas (2015:121) asserts that liberal rights and democratic participation are mutually reinforcing: “the system of rights... secures private and public autonomy simultaneously.” That is, freedom of speech and association (liberal rights) enable open deliberation, which in turn legitimizes democratic decision-making. Similarly, Rawls (1993:3) argued that a “well-ordered society” requires both fair procedures and substantive rights: “each person possesses an inviolability founded on justice that even the welfare of society as a whole cannot override.”

Modern liberal democracies institutionalize this balance. Constitutions protect minorities, while elections express majority preferences. Independent judiciaries ensure that legislative outcomes respect individual liberties, and civil society mediates between state and citizen. As Plattner (1998) notes, “liberalism and democracy are like two sides of the same coin—mutually dependent but conceptually distinct. Nevertheless, given these tensions, the question arises: can liberalism and democracy be reconciled in a meaningful, sustainable way?”

The Case for Complementarity: A Liberal-Communitarian Synthesis

The historical and philosophical tensions between liberalism and democracy have generated intense debate about how to reconcile the individual’s moral autonomy with the community’s collective will. Liberalism emphasizes individual rights, limited government, and negative freedom, while democracy, particularly in its majoritarian and participatory forms, stresses political equality, civic responsibility, and popular sovereignty. This dualism often breeds conflicts, especially in pluralistic societies where competing conceptions of the good life coexist. In light of this, the search for complementarity, a synthesis that balances liberal and communitarian concerns, becomes necessary. Oseni Afisi’s reflections on the liberal-communitarian debate, particularly his reading of Karl Popper’s idea of freedom, offer a notable but limited attempt at such synthesis. In his discussion of the liberal-communitarian debate, Afisi takes a deliberate conciliatory stance, recognizing that neither liberalism nor communitarianism in its pure form offers a sufficient basis for the flourishing of human society. To illustrate this, Afisi turns to Karl Popper’s

concept of freedom, which he (2016) presents as a philosophical bridge between individualism and communal responsibility. Afisi writes: “Popper’s concept of freedom is a balance between negative freedom and positive freedom. It is a balance between elements of individualism and communitarianism. It is a liberal-communitarian idea of freedom” (Afisi, 2016).

Popper’s dual notion of freedom—as freedom from coercion (negative liberty) and freedom to develop within community (positive liberty), resonates with attempts to reconcile the rights of individuals with the needs of the collective. According to Afisi, this hybrid freedom reflects the lived reality of political societies, where neither abstract autonomy nor absolute communal integration is sustainable on its own (Agunbiade,2025:60-63).

Afisi’s insight is crucial for understanding the internal dialectic of liberal democracy. In a democratic society, individuals are granted rights and freedoms, but those freedoms are realized within a social context that demands shared responsibility, public deliberation, and constitutional limits. His appeal to Popper’s middle ground affirms the interdependence of the self and society, where liberty is not merely self-directed action, but also freedom to participate meaningfully in the social and political life of a community (Agunbiade,2025:60-63).

Liberal democracy is often praised as a system that safeguards both individual liberty and popular participation, but in practice, these two principles can be in tension. Liberalism, with its focus on inalienable rights and the rule of law, can limit the reach of democratic decisions to protect minorities and secure freedom of conscience. Democracy, with its emphasis on majority rule and popular sovereignty, can challenge liberal constraints when those constraints appear to block collective aspirations.

In this light, Afisi’s call for a liberal-communitarian idea of freedom mirrors the underlying logic of a synthesis model—an approach where individual autonomy and communal values are not mutually exclusive but mutually sustaining. A liberal-communitarian synthesis thus helps to resolve the binary opposition between rights and responsibilities, self and society, freedom and solidarity. This synthesis is particularly vital in pluralistic democracies where diverse worldviews must coexist under a shared constitutional and political order.

Conclusion

The persistent tension between liberalism and democracy, between the rights of the individual and the will of the collective, has long shaped the contours of modern political thought. Liberalism safeguards the inviolability of personal freedom, while democracy asserts the legitimacy of public will and shared governance. In their pure forms, these doctrines risk mutual erosion: liberalism may become detached from civic life, and democracy may descend into unchecked majoritarianism. Oseni Afisi's contribution to this enduring debate is both valuable and thought-provoking. By drawing on Karl Popper's concept of freedom as a balance between negative and positive liberty, Afisi attempts to synthesize individual autonomy with communal engagement. His liberal-communitarian approach provides a philosophical space where the self is free not in isolation but through meaningful participation in society. This framework challenges the false binary that often characterizes the liberal-communitarian divide, offering instead a nuanced model of coexistence and mutual reinforcement. Such a model is not merely theoretical; it is essential for the survival and flourishing of pluralistic societies. In the face of rising populism, cultural fragmentation, and democratic backsliding, liberal democracies must learn to balance the moral worth of individual rights with the binding force of social solidarity. Complementarity, understood as a dynamic, evolving, and context-sensitive relationship between self and society, offers the most promising pathway forward. It affirms that in a just society, liberty and equality, autonomy and belonging, must walk hand in hand

References

- Afisi, O. T. (2016) "Popper, Liberal-Communitarianism, and Beyond the Politics of Liberalism." *Philosophia: E-Journal of Philosophy and Culture* 67–86.
- Agunbiade, Saheed A. "The Problem of Individual-Community Rights in Bernard Matolino's Limited Communitarianism." *APPON Philosophical Quarterly* 3, no. 3 (2024a).
- Agunbiade Saheed A. (2024) "On the Definition of African Philosophy: An Interrogation of Analytic and Traditional Schools." *LASU Journal of Religions and Peace Studies* 6, no. 6
- Agunbiade Saheed A. (2025). Beyond the Liberal-Communitarianism of Oseni Afisi: A Complementarist Reconstruction of Individual-Community Rights. *Philosophy and Praxis*, 15(1), 20.
- Ake, C. (2000). *The Feasibility of Democracy in Africa*. Dakar: CODESRIA.

- Bayo, O. (2000). "A Critique of Democracy." In J. K. Omotehinse (Ed.), *Introduction to Social Political Philosophy (African and Blacks in Diaspora)* (pp. 147–153). Lagos: Samtech Communications Ltd.
- Bobbio, N. (1990). *Liberalism and Democracy*. London: Verso.
- Chilles, J. (2016). "The Future of Democracy in Africa." ISS Paper 19, Institute for Security Studies.
- Dahl, R. A. (1971). *Polyarchy: Participation and Opposition*. Yale University Press.
- Dahl, R. A. (1989). *Democracy and Its Critics*. Yale University Press.
- Gray, J. (1995). *Liberalism* (2nd ed.). University of Minnesota Press.
- Gyekye, K. (1997). *Tradition and Modernity: Philosophical Reflections on the African Experience*. Oxford University Press.
- Held, D. (2006). *Models of Democracy* (3rd ed.). Polity Press.
- Heywood, A. (2012). *Political Ideologies: An Introduction* (5th ed.). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Lincoln, A. (1863). The Gettysburg Address. In R. B. Basler (Ed.), *The Collected Works of Abraham Lincoln*, Vol. 7. Rutgers University Press.
- Locke, J. (1689). *Two Treatises of Government*.
- Locke, J. (1980). *Second Treatise of Government* (C. B. Macpherson, Ed.). Hackett Publishing. (Original work published 1689)
- Mill, J. S. (1859). *On Liberty*.
- Mill, J. S. (1991). *Considerations on Representative Government*. Prometheus Books. (Original work published 1861)
- Mill, J. S. (2003). *On Liberty*. *Penguin Classics*. (Original work published 1859)
- Minogue, K. (1996). "Democracy." In A. Kuper & J. Kuper (Eds.), *The Social Sciences Encyclopedia* (2nd ed., p. 172). Routledge.
- Montesquieu. (1989). *The Spirit of the Laws* (A. Cohler, B. Miller & H. Stone, Trans.). Cambridge University Press. (Original work published 1748)
- Mouffe, C. (2000). *The Democratic Paradox*. London: Verso.
- Mouk, Y. (2018). *The People vs. Democracy*. Harvard University Press.
- Merriam-Webster Dictionary. (2023). Democracy.
- Owolabi, K. A. (1999). "The Quest for Democracy in Africa: A Theoretical Exploration." In K. Ogbinaka (Ed.), *African Studies Monograph* (pp. 1–30). Lagos: Obaroh and Ogbinaka.
- Pickles, D. (1970). *Democracy*. London: Methuen & Co.
- Rawls, J. (1971). *A Theory of Justice*. Harvard University Press.
- Rousseau, J.-J. (1997). *The Social Contract* (G. D. H. Cole, Trans.). Wordsworth Classics. (Original work published 1762)
- Sandel, M. J. (1982). *Liberalism and the Limits of Justice*. Cambridge University Press.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (1942). *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy*. Harper & Brothers.
- Sen, A. (1999). *Development as Freedom*. Oxford University Press.

-
- Taylor, C. (1992). *Sources of the Self: The Making of the Modern Identity*. Harvard University Press.
- Tocqueville, A. de (1835). *Democracy in America* (Reeve Translation).
- Walzer, M. (1983). *Spheres of Justice: A Defense of Pluralism and Equality*. Basic Books.
- Wiredu, K. (1996). *Cultural Universals and Particulars: An African Perspective*. Indiana University Press.
- Zakaria, F. (2003). *The Future of Freedom: Illiberal Democracy at Home and Abroad*. W. W. Norton & Co.